

Computational micromechanics evaluation of the effect of fibre shape on the transverse strength of unidirectional composites: an approach to virtual materials design

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Abstract

Computational micromechanics of composites is an emerging tool required for virtual materials design (VMD) in order to address the effect of the involved variables before materials are manufactured. This strategy will avoid unnecessary costs reducing trial-and-error campaigns leading to fast material developments for tailored properties. In this work, the effect of the fibre cross section on the transverse behavior of unidirectional fibre composites has been evaluated by means of computational micromechanics. To this end, periodic representative volume elements containing uniform and random dispersions of 50% of parallel non-circular fibres with lobular, polygonal and elliptical shapes were generated. Fibre/matrix interface failure as well as matrix plasticity/damage were considered as the fundamental failure mechanisms operating at the microscale under transverse loading. Circular fibres showed the best averaged behaviour although lobular fibres exhibited superior per-

formance in transverse compression mainly due to the higher tensile thermal residual stresses generated during cooling at the fibre/matrix interface.

Keywords:

Non-circular fibres, C. Micro-mechanics, B. Strength, B. Residual/internal stress

1. Introduction

Polymer matrices reinforced with high performance fibres or FRP's are preferred candidates in structural applications where the strength to weight ratio leads the structural design process. One of the main drawbacks regarding the use of these materials is their complex mechanical behaviour, hardly predictable, which depends on the constituents properties, fibres, matrix and interfaces, as well as their spatial distribution within the material. Manufacturing conditions also play an important role and are responsible for the generation of defects in the form of voids, interfacial debonds, resin pockets or dry fibre areas which are considered detrimental for the final performance of the material. The mechanical response of FRP's is, obviously, strongly influenced by the mechanical properties of the high performance fibres used (carbon, glass, aramid, etc.) albeit their spatial distribution, tow architecture and cross section governs the basic deformation and failure mechanisms [1].

Since the discover of high-performance carbon fibres, the composite production process has been optimized to maximize their intrinsic mechanical, thermal and electrical properties. Despite these efforts, the morphology of the reinforcing fibres has barely evolved since its discovery and most de-

20 velopments in this field were kept at a basic research level due to major
21 manufacturing difficulties [2, 3].

22 Pitch-based carbon fibres with different non-circular cross section have
23 been extensively studied by Edie and Dunham [4]. This research group deter-
24 mined the main manufacturing parameters as the mesophase pitch viscosity,
25 winding speed and temperature controlling the fibre properties using a lab-
26 scale set-up. Trilobal and octolobal fibres were obtained from the extrusion
27 of the filaments from different cross section spinnerets [5, 6]. From a mechan-
28 ical point of view, trilobal and round fibres respond differently to increasing
29 process temperatures (i.e. carbonization). Trilobal fibres exhibited a higher
30 longitudinal elastic modulus and tensile strength than standard circular ones
31 (744 GPa and 2.72 GPa, respectively being 1900 °C the carbonization tem-
32 perature). Comparing to the radial fibre texture, typical of carbon fibres
33 spun from mesophase pitch, the microstructure of trilobal carbon fibres does
34 not emanate radially from a centre point, but instead grows up from three
35 lines extending from the tip of each lobe. Ribbon-shaped mesophase-pitch
36 fibres have also been produced, obtaining a line-origin transversal texture
37 which enhances their transport properties [6]. Recent studies demonstrated
38 the possibility to manufacture X-type fibres which theoretically can increase
39 $\approx 3-8$ times the fracture energy of cementitious composites when compared
40 to standard circular fibres [7].

41 Hollow carbon fibres can be fabricated by several methods such as coaxial
42 electro-spinning, bi-polymer blends or fibre templates. A 60% hollow carbon
43 fibre embedded in an epoxy matrix ($V_f \approx 40\%$) can result in a composite ma-
44 terial with a density as low as 850 Kg/m³ as compared with the 1600 Kg/m³

45 of the standard fully dense non-hollow composite [3] demonstrating the high
46 potential for structural lightweighting. The fibre manufacturer Toray devel-
47 oped hollow carbon fibres with tensile strength and modulus of 2.2 and 190
48 GPa, respectively, by carbonizing bi-component wet spun sheath-core fibres,
49 with PAN as the sheath and PVA (polyvinyl alcohol) as the core [3].

50 Circular, hollow and C-shaped carbon fibres were also manufactured by
51 melt-spun of isotropic pitch [8, 9, 10]. Composite materials were produced by
52 hot-press consolidation of prepregs prepared with this set of non-circular fi-
53 bres by drum winding. Interlaminar shear strength specimens (ILSS) demon-
54 strated that C-shaped CFRP's perform better as compared with circular base
55 line composites manufactured maintaining the same equivalent cross section
56 (the C-shape resin contact area was 2.72 times larger than the circular cross
57 section with the same area [9]). In addition, C-shaped carbon fibre compos-
58 ites exhibited excellent energy absorption under impact as well as better fibre
59 wettability and thermal conductivity than round fibres [9, 10]. Patterned car-
60 bon fibres with customized surface contours were produced by [3, 11] using
61 a combination of a bi-component fibre melt spinning and a sulphonation
62 with polyethylene (PE) precursors. By properly designing the flow path
63 and spinneret geometry, carbon fibres with trilobal, flower, and gear-shaped
64 cross-sections in the diameter range from 0.5 to 20 μm have been produced.
65 Although carbon fibres produced by this method have not reached yet stan-
66 dard mechanical properties (tensile strength 1.1 GPa and modulus 103 GPa),
67 the customized fibre geometry may extend their application in different fields.

68 Manufacturing of structural composites with non-circular fibres is still
69 kept at laboratory scale limited by the scalability of the production process

70 as compared with conventional circular fibres. Therefore, material optimiza-
71 tion to achieve tailored properties based on trial and error campaigns will not
72 be suitable at this scale and a more efficient strategy based on virtual ma-
73 terial design and Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME)
74 can be adopted instead, at least during the first stages of the evaluation pro-
75 cess [12]. Moreover, isolation of the effects of the fibre cross section on the
76 composite performance may not be possible as the interface and matrix prop-
77 erties may be affected by the fibre shape during the manufacturing process.
78 Computational micromechanics is emerging in recent years as a powerful tool
79 to predict the influence of the constituent properties and the fibre shape on
80 the ply behaviour under different loading conditions. This approach is based
81 on the numerical simulation of the mechanical response of a *representative*
82 *volume element* (RVE) of the composite microstructure [1, 13, 14, 15] by
83 means of the finite element method. As a result, this numerical strategy
84 considers detailed information of the microstructure and constituent proper-
85 ties, inherited from micromechanical characterization of the fibres [16, 17],
86 matrix [18] and interface [19, 20]. Computational micromechanics is used
87 in this work to ascertain the effect of the shape of reinforcing fibres on the
88 transverse tension and compression strength in carbon/epoxy unidirectional
89 plies of 50% fibre volume fraction.

90 **2. Computational micromechanics**

91 The micromechanical model developed is based on the analysis of a repre-
92 sentative volume element (RVE) containing a periodic and random dispersion
93 of parallel fibres embedded in a polymer matrix representing the transversal

94 section of an unidirectional composite ply [1, 13, 14]. In this work, the vol-
95 ume fraction of fibre reinforcement was set to 50% in all simulations, a value
96 that is usually attained in manufacturing of common structural FRP's. No
97 attempt to ascertain the influence of fibre volume fraction on the transverse
98 strength properties was done in this paper although damage triggering mech-
99 anisms by debonding/matrix shear yielding should not be strongly affected
100 in this case.

101 The RVE dimensions were large enough to ensure simulation results were
102 size independent in a statistical sense, without exceeding the computational
103 resources, to allow fast and efficient computations. A RVE of $L_0 = 58\mu m$ in
104 length was enough to capture the fundamental fracture mechanisms under
105 transverse tension (interface failure) and compression (matrix shear yielding)
106 assuming an average diameter of the fibres of $d_f = 7.19 \mu m$ (representative
107 of AS4 carbon fibres). Therefore, a minimum of 8 fibres along each of the
108 axis of the plane of transverse isotropy ($L_0/d_f \geq 8$) are distributed (a total
109 of 42 in the RVE), 1. The RVE was extruded along the fibre axis with a
110 thickness of $0.5 \mu m$. The results were compared with RVE's containing 80
111 fibres to ensure that the size of the RVE did not influence significantly the
112 model predictions.

113 *2.1. Boundary conditions*

114 Periodicity of the mechanical fields is guaranteed through the applica-
115 tion of the corresponding periodic boundary conditions (PBC). PBC are
116 imposed between opposite faces of the RVE to ensure the continuity with
117 the neighbour RVE's as a jigsaw puzzle. For a given RVE with dimensions of
118 $w_0 \times L_0 \times L_0$, the periodic boundary conditions are imposed as nodal displace-

119 ments relations between opposite RVE faces using the following constraint
 120 equations:

$$121 \quad \vec{u}(0, X_2, X_3) - \vec{u}(w_0, X_2, X_3) = \vec{U}_1 \quad (1)$$

$$122 \quad \vec{u}(X_1, 0, X_3) - \vec{u}(X_1, L_0, X_3) = \vec{U}_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{u}(X_1, X_2, 0) - \vec{u}(X_1, X_2, L_0) = \vec{U}_3 \quad (3)$$

123 where X_1, X_2, X_3 are the coordinates axis ($0 < X_1 < w_0, 0 < X_2 < L_0,$
 124 $0 < X_3 < L_0$) and \vec{U}_i is the displacement of the master node i (with $i =$
 125 $1, 2, 3$). As a result, three master nodes are defined on the three dimensional
 126 unit cell: $MN_1(w_0, 0, 0), MN_2(0, L_0, 0), MN_3(0, 0, L_0)$. Uniaxial tension and
 127 compression in both transverse directions (X_2 and X_3) can be imposed to the
 128 RVE by applying the appropriate displacements to the master nodes. For
 129 instance, uniaxial tension or compression along the X_2 direction is imposed
 130 with $\vec{U}_2 = (0, \pm\delta_2, 0), \vec{U}_1 = (u_1, 0, 0)$ and $\vec{U}_3 = (0, 0, u_3)$, where δ_2 (Fig. 1)
 131 stands for the tensile displacement applied, and u_1 and u_3 the lateral Poisson
 132 contractions obtained under the surface integral of the traction vector

$$\int \vec{t} dS = \vec{0} \text{ on } X_1 = 0 \text{ and } X_3 = 0 \quad (4)$$

133 Initially, a homogeneous thermal step is applied without external loading
 134 to reproduce the cooling down process from the curing (175°C) to service
 135 temperature (15°C). This thermal step of $\Delta T = -160^\circ\text{C}$ induces a residual
 136 thermal stress microfield as a result of the mismatch of the thermo-elastic
 137 constants of fibres and matrix.

138 *2.2. Constitutive models of fibre, matrix and interface*

139 RVE's are discretized using finite elements in Abaqus/Standard [21]. The
 140 matrix is modelled with 8-node fully integrated brick isoparametric elements
 141 (C3D8), while the fibres are meshed with 6-node fully integrated wedge
 142 isoparametric elements (C3D6). The fibre/matrix interface debonding was
 143 simulated with 8-node cohesive isoparametric elements (COH3D8) inserted
 144 at the interfaces between fibres and matrix. Perfect and homogeneous con-
 145 tact between fibres and matrix was assumed without any gaps at the inter-
 146 face. Carbon fibres behave as linear elastic and transversely isotropic solids
 147 and the thermoelastic constants of AS4 carbon fibres are reported in Ta-
 148 ble 1 [22]. They were kept constant with the deformation imposed during
 149 the transverse-to-the-fibres loading neglecting any possible non-linearity due
 150 to non-Hookean fibre behaviour [23]. In addition, no fibre fracture is taken
 151 into account in agreement with experiments carried out in AS4/8552 [1].
 152 Fibre/matrix interface failure is taken into account using a cohesive crack
 153 approach, Fig. 2a. To this end, cohesive elements inserted at the interface
 154 between fibres are governed by a mixed-mode traction-separation law where
 155 damage onset is controlled by the following stress criterion [24]:

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{N}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{S}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_t}{S}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

156 where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ stands for McCauly brackets defined as $\langle x \rangle = \max(0, x)$, t_n is
 157 the normal traction and, t_s and t_t are the shear components of the traction
 158 vector. N is the normal strength and S is the shear strength assumed to
 159 be equal in both shear directions s and t . In addition, damage evolution is
 160 governed by a Benzeggagh-Kenane [25] law as

$$G^c = G_n^c + (G_s^c - G_n^c) \cdot \left(\frac{2G_s}{G_n + 2G_s} \right)^{\eta_{BK}} \quad (6)$$

161 where η_{BK} is the Benzeggagh-Kenane power exponent, G_n^c and G_s^c are the
162 normal and shear fracture energies respectively, and G_n and G_s the reciprocal
163 work under mixed mode propagation. The interface parameters used in the
164 simulations are presented in Table 2 [26]. Finally, the polymer matrix be-
165 haviour is represented using the Lubliner damaged/plasticity model included
166 in Abaqus/Standard [21]. This constitutive equation allows the material to
167 behave as quasi-brittle when subjected to dominant tensile stress while it
168 shows elasto-plastic behaviour under pressure confinement and compressive
169 loads. The tensile response is, therefore, linear and elastic with elastic modu-
170 lus and Poisson ratio E_m and ν_m until the tensile failure stress σ_{t0} is reached,
171 Fig. 2b. Beyond this point, a quasi-brittle softening is induced in the ma-
172 terial being G_t the matrix fracture energy. Under uniaxial compression the
173 response is linear up to the initial yield limit σ_{c0} . Then, stress hardening
174 takes place until the ultimate stress value is reached σ_{cu} , Fig. 2b. The ma-
175 trix plasticity/damage model parameters used in the simulations are reported
176 in Table 3 [19, 26].

177 2.3. Microstructure generation

178 Four different families of fibre section geometries were considered in this
179 work as represented in Fig. 3 including standard circular, lobular (2, 3 and 4-
180 lobed), polygonal (3 and 4 edges) with smoothed vertex, and elliptical with
181 0.75 eccentricity ratio. The equivalent diameter of non-circular fibres was
182 kept constant and equal to the standard circular fibres ($\approx 7.19I \mu m$ for AS4

183 carbon fibre) for comparison purposes. A new set of distributions with 2-
184 lobed and elliptical fibres aligned in a fixed direction is presented to study
185 the effect of cross section orientation on the overall transversal behaviour
186 of the composite material. The detailed geometry definition of the lobular
187 and polygonal fibres is presented in Fig. 4a and 4b, respectively, with the
188 corresponding dimensions used in the simulations (fillet radii, vertex, etc).

189 It was assumed that the microstructure of the composite was given by a
190 indefinite translation of the RVE along the two coordinate axes and thus the
191 fibre positions within the RVE should keep this periodicity condition. Fibre
192 centres were generated randomly and sequentially according to the nearest
193 neighbour algorithm (NNA) [27]. No fibre-to-fibre contacts were included in
194 the model and the position of each new fibre was accepted if the distance
195 between neighboring fibre surfaces was greater than $0.05 \cdot d_f$. The assump-
196 tions made on idealization of the microstructure could potentially have an
197 impact, for instance, in fibre-to-fibre contacts resulting from a deficient resin
198 impregnation or in a highly clustered fibre dispersions, but these effects are
199 considered out scope of this work. This restriction ensures an adequate mesh
200 discretization of these regions [1, 13, 14]. In addition, the distance between
201 the fibre surface and the RVE edges should be greater than $0.15 \cdot d_f$ to avoid
202 distorted finite elements during meshing. Fibres intersecting the RVE edges
203 were split and complemented at the opposite sides of the square RVE to
204 create a periodic microstructure. New fibres were added until the desired
205 volume fraction of 50% was reached. The model assumed an homogeneous
206 dispersion of non-circular fibres within the epoxy matrix and does not take
207 into account local volume fraction variations related to the presence of fibre

208 clusters or resin rich regions

209 **3. Unidirectional ply behaviour prediction**

210 Five random RVE's for each of the different fibre cross sections consid-
211 ered were generated for the analysis. Simulations were carried out with
212 Abaqus/Standard [21] within the framework of the finite deformations the-
213 ory with the initial unstressed state as reference. In the first step, the RVE
214 was subjected to a homogeneous temperature change of -160°C from the
215 stress-free temperature down to ambient temperature which was followed
216 by the application of the individual loading step (transverse tension and
217 compression along X_2 and X_3 directions). In addition, simulations were per-
218 formed with the same fibre distributions but without the thermal step to
219 ascertain the effect of residual stresses on the mechanical performance of the
220 unidirectional plies.

221 *3.1. Ply thermal residual stress*

222 Residual stresses appeared in the simulated RVE's during the thermal
223 step due to the mismatch between the thermoelastic constants of the fibres
224 and the matrix. The matrix thermally contracts more than the fibres during
225 the temperature drop and this strain incompatibility is solved with the gen-
226 eration of a residual stresses field at the micro level. The maximum principal
227 stress field upon cooling is depicted in Fig. 5a for a 3-lobed fibre distribu-
228 tion. This plot clearly evidences tension and compression stress states in
229 the matrix and the fibre respectively. Normal (t_n or interfacial normal stress
230 INS) and shear (t_s or interfacial shear stress ISS) stresses are generated also

231 at the fibre/matrix interfaces which could potentially affect the overall be-
232 haviour of the unidirectional ply in the subsequent loading step. Generally
233 speaking, high compressive normal stresses appeared between two closely
234 neighbour fibres being then tensile normal stress distribution in this situ-
235 ation comparatively lower, Fig. 5b. In addition, interfacial shear stresses
236 appeared surrounding the regions of maximum normal compressive stresses
237 to accommodate the high normal stress gradient along the fibre/matrix in-
238 terface, Fig. 5c.

239 The summary of the maximum interface stresses (normal and shear) at-
240 tained during the cooling step for the different fibre cross shape analysed
241 is presented in Fig. 6. The values, average and standard deviation, repre-
242 sented in the plot were obtained from the local maximum of the interface
243 stress obtained in each of the five realizations computed being the error bars
244 attributed to the fibre position and spatial distribution.

245 The results show that maximum normal stress values in tension $\approx 28 -$
246 29MPa were attained in those microstructures containing lobular fibres and
247 this effect was essentially attributed to the geometry of the fibres in the con-
248 cave regions of their perimeter. When the fibre interfaces were flat or con-
249 vex, the normal stresses were considerably reduced as compared with lobular
250 ($\approx 16 - 18\text{MPa}$ for polygonal and $\approx 11 - 13\text{MPa}$ for circular and elliptical).
251 Very interestingly, the higher the number of lobes of such type of fibres, the
252 higher the maximum compressive and shear interfacial stresses obtained. No
253 significant differences of maximum residual stresses were detected in aligned
254 microstructures (2-lobed and elliptical) when compared with equivalent ran-
255 dom distributions.

256 It should be mentioned that in all cases, the interface stress level ob-
257 tained was moderate and the interface damage initiation criterion was not
258 fulfilled (Eq. 5) being the overall behaviour of the unidirectional ply elastic
259 during the temperature drop. Previous studies have demonstrated that ther-
260 mal residual stress at the interface may critically affect mechanical response.
261 Thermal compressive stresses provide higher transverse tensile strength [28],
262 while the presence of the interface shear stress contributes to the early onset
263 of damage when transverse loading is applied [29]. In this respect, an *a priori*
264 difference in the transverse tensile strength of lobular fibres configurations is
265 expected.

266 3.2. Ply transverse tensile loading

267 The response of the unidirectional plies under transverse tension is linear
268 and elastic up to the onset of damage which takes place at moderate trans-
269 verse strains of $\approx 1\%$. This transverse tensile failure is essentially brittle
270 and is produced by the localization of interface cracks at the poles of the
271 fibres in a given section of the material. Interface cracks are rapidly local-
272 ized in a given section which is followed by tearing of the ligaments between
273 adjacent fibres [19]. These failure mechanisms are accurately reproduced by
274 the RVE simulations. For instance, Fig. 7a and b represent the final crack
275 configuration at the failure point for an homogeneous dispersion of aligned
276 and randomly dispersed elliptical fibres, respectively. Interface cracks were
277 triggered at the fibre poles and rapidly were interconnected when tearing of
278 matrix ligaments between fibres occurred. The failure mechanisms are the
279 same irrespective of the shape of the fibres, although slight differences in the
280 crack paths were observed depending on the geometry connecting the poles

281 of the fibres (Fig. 7c and d).

282 The results shown in Fig. 8a represent the transverse tensile strength Y_t
283 for the RVE's containing different fibre cross sections. Circular fibres exhib-
284 ited the most balanced tensile strength in the two directions X_2 and X_3 for
285 all the cross sections analysed and this effect can be endorsed to the lower
286 stress concentration created by the circular fibres when compared with polyg-
287 onal or lobular. For instance, approximate knock-down factors of $\approx 17\%$ and
288 $\approx 8\%$ are obtained for triangular and quadrilateral fibres, respectively, al-
289 though this effect can be even more detrimental on the material performance
290 depending on the fillet radii used (Fig. 4b).

291 All configurations showed transversely isotropic behaviour with the excep-
292 tion of the aligned 2-lobed and elliptical fibres. In both cases, the transverse
293 strength was similar $\approx 68\text{MPa}$ in the X_2 direction although an important
294 reduction in the transverse strength in the orthogonal direction X_3 can be
295 observed (33% and 15% for 2-lobed and elliptical, respectively). This ef-
296 fect can be attributed in lobular fibres to the initial residual tensile stress
297 (INS) which prompts the earlier interface failure as compared with polygonal
298 sections (Fig. 6).

299 Simulations were repeated without the initial thermal step in order to
300 ascertain the effect of residual stress on the final transverse strength of the
301 fibre distributions. Average values and standard deviations corresponding
302 to all the fibre realizations in the two directions were depicted in Fig. 8a
303 including the results with and without thermal temperature drop. In all
304 cases, the transverse tensile strength decreased in the absence of the thermal
305 residual stress indicating a strong shielding effect due to their compressive

306 nature. Very interestingly, circular and ellipsoidal fibres presented the highest
307 thermal residual stress effect (+15 ~ 20%) and this effect can be probably
308 attributed to the larger ratios between the compressive and tensile normal
309 interface stress.

310 *3.3. Ply transverse compressive loading*

311 Experimental evidences demonstrated that unidirectional plies subjected
312 to transverse compression fail after significant non-linear deformation (\approx
313 2 – 4%) by the development of matrix shear bands where severe plastic de-
314 formation and fibre/matrix interface decohesion occurs. The final failure
315 is produced through an inclined crack of $\approx 56\%$ with respect to the plane
316 perpendicular to the loading axis in the case of standard carbon/epoxy com-
317 posites [1]. RVE's subjected to transverse compression failed following the
318 aforementioned mechanisms as it is illustrated in Fig. 9 for a homogeneous
319 dispersion of circular, 3-polygonal and 2-lobed (aligned and randomly dis-
320 persed) where the contours of accumulated plastic strain for an overall strain
321 of $\approx 4\%$ are plotted for comparison purposes. Interfacial voids controlled the
322 strength of the material leading thus to the localization of the matrix plastic
323 strain between adjacent fibres triggering the final percolation shear band in
324 the matrix within the RVE.

325 Generally, the results show that lobular fibres unidirectional plies pre-
326 sented the best transverse compressive performance and this effect can be
327 directly attributed to the pre-tensile residual stress induced in the lobular fi-
328 bres microstructures (Fig. 5) increasing the response under compression. The
329 results in terms of transverse yield strength, Y_c , for all the fibre geometries
330 analysed are summarized in Fig. 8b. All the configurations showed equivalent

331 transversely isotropic behaviour, in both directions X_2 and X_3 of the RVE
332 with the exception of the 2-lobed and elliptical aligned distributions which
333 showed some degree of anisotropic behaviour caused by the alignment of the
334 fibre cross sections.

335 Plastic shear bands are more intense in the case of the 3-polygonal dis-
336 tributions where strong strain concentrations appeared at the fillet radius
337 areas, Fig. 9b, jumping from fibre to fibre resulting in a final knock-down
338 factor on the transverse compressive strength, Y_c , of $\approx 13\%$ when compared
339 with standard circular fibres, Fig. 8b. On the other hand, 2-lobed aligned
340 fibre distributions exhibited the highest enhancement ($\approx 16\%$) in the trans-
341 verse compression strength in both directions when compared with standard
342 circular fibres, Fig. 8b being the shear bands more distributed within the
343 RVE, Fig. 9c and d.

344 The influence of the residual stress step was limited for the case of the
345 transverse compression for all the cases analysed and this effect was at-
346 tributed to the fact that thermal-elastic residual stress were partially re-
347 lieved due to the plastic behaviour of the polymer matrix under confined
348 compressive stress state. Shear banding occurs following the same mecha-
349 nisms promoted by interfacial residual stresses but plastic deformation help
350 to reduce the subsequent effect on the compressive strength. As a result, the
351 transverse compressive strength, Y_c , was not strongly affected Fig. 8b.

352 4. Concluding remarks

353 The mechanical behaviour of a fibre-reinforced composite lamina under
354 transverse tension and compression has been simulated by means of computa-

355 tional micromechanics. This approach explicitly considers fibres distribution
356 within the material as well as matrix, fibre and interface thermomechanical
357 properties which are included in the simulations through the appropriate
358 constitutive models. The simulations demonstrated the key role played by
359 the two dominant damage mechanisms (debonding at the interface and shear
360 band formation in the matrix) controlling the composite strength. In this
361 work it has been observed the increase of higher tensile residual stresses along
362 the concave interfaces of lobular fibres, up to +260% compared to circular
363 fibres. Under transverse tension, 2-lobed and elliptical fibres show a high
364 orthotropic behaviour when aligned reaching +10% tensile strength in the
365 alignment direction (X_2), but it drops around $-12 \sim 25\%$ in the perpendicular
366 direction (X_3). Regarding transverse compression, all the microstructures
367 analysed show almost in-plane isotropic behaviour. The most remarkable re-
368 sult is the increase of compressive strength in microstructures with lobular
369 fibres up to +20% compared to circular fibres.

370 The results presented in this paper not only show the ability of these mod-
371 els to reproduce the physical failure mechanisms under transverse loading,
372 but also the potential to virtually predict the influence of design variables,
373 such as fibres shape, on the mechanical response of a unidirectional lamina.
374 Virtual material design opens the possibility of partially replacing or reducing
375 costly and time-consuming experimental testing campaigns. This strategy al-
376 lows the exploration of several possibilities in microstructural design such as:
377 (i) analysis of hybrid composite microstructures, (ii) reproduction of multi-
378 axial stress states and calculation of failure envelopes, (iii) quantification of
379 the effect of fibre volume fraction on ply properties. The coupling of this

380 numerical tool with optimization algorithms will allow the identification of
381 optimal microstructural configurations. Nevertheless, further validation of
382 these techniques is required to ascertain numerical results and determine the
383 reliability of the numerical tool.

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Table 1: Material properties of AS4 carbon fibres [22].

E_1	E_2	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	G_{12}	G_{23}	α_1	α_2
(GPa)	(GPa)			(GPa)	(GPa)	(10^{-6} K^{-1})	(10^{-6} K^{-1})
231.6	12.97	0.3	0.46	11.3	4.45	-0.9	7.2

Table 2: Material properties of fibre-matrix interface [26].

N	S	E_{nn}	E_{ss}	G_n^c	G_s^c	η_{BK}
(MPa)	(MPa)	(GPa)	(GPa)	(J/m^2)	(J/m^2)	
42	63	100	100	2	30	1.2

Table 3: Parameters of the damaged plasticity model that characterize the matrix [19, 26].

E_m	ν_m	α	σ_{t0}	G_t	σ_{c0}	σ_{cu}
(GPa)		(10^{-6} K^{-1})	(MPa)	(J/m^2)	(MPa)	(MPa)
5.07	0.35	52.0	121	90	176	180

Figure 1: Schematic 2D view of the model showing the detail of the fibres distribution, FEM mesh, cohesive interface and periodic boundary conditions (PBC). The transverse tension loading case along X_2 direction is illustrated.

Figure 2: Schematics of the linear traction-separation law for the cohesive interface (a) and stress-strain curve for the matrix (b).

Figure 3: Representative volume element example of each microstructure configuration: (a) circular, (b) 2-lobed, (c) 2-lobed aligned, (d) 3-lobed, (e) 4-lobed, (f) 3-polygonal, (g) 4-polygonal, (h) elliptical and (i) elliptical aligned.

Cross-section	α ($^\circ$)	d_{eff} (μm)	r (μm)	L (μm)
2-lobed	90	7.19	2.48	9.92
3-lobed	60	7.19	2.01	8.65
4-lobed	45	7.19	1.70	8.20
3-Polygonal	60	7.19	1.47	8.83
4-Polygonal	45	7.19	1.64	7.91

Figure 4: Geometry definition and dimensions for non-circular fibres.

Figure 5: Residual stresses after thermal step in a microstructure with 3-lobed fibres: (a) Maximum principal stress field, (b) detail of interfacial normal stress (INS), (c) detail of interfacial shear stress (ISS)

Figure 6: Maximum residual thermal stresses at fibre/matrix interface.

Figure 7: Equivalent plastic strain (shown grey-scaled) and interfacial damage (shown red) under transverse horizontal tension ($\varepsilon_t \simeq 1.0\%$):(a) circular fibres. (b) 3-polygonal fibres. (c) 2-lobed aligned fibres. (d) 2-lobed fibres.

(a) Transverse tension strength.

(b) Transverse compression strength.

Figure 8: Effect of residual stresses on the transverse strength of non circular fibres RVE's:
a) Tensile strength, b) compressive strength.

Figure 9: Equivalent plastic strain (shown grey-scaled) and interfacial damage (shown red) under transverse horizontal compression ($\varepsilon_c \simeq 4.0\%$): (a) circular fibres. (b) 3-polygonal fibres. (c) 2-lobed aligned fibres. (d) 2-lobed fibres.

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